

% NSGA-II Algorithm

```
t = 1 % Start generation counter
Initialize Pt % Randomly generate and evaluate a population of parents, size N
 $\mathcal{F} = \text{non\_dominated\_sorting}(P_t)$  % Identify non-dominated fronts  $\mathcal{F}_i$ ,  $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, etc.$ 
crowding\_distance\_assignment( $\mathcal{F}$ ) % Calculate crowding distance for each front  $\mathcal{F}_i$ 
 $Q_t = \text{genetic\_operators}(P_t, \mathcal{F})$  % Create an offspring population by applying genetic operators to  $P_t$ 
 $R_t = P_t \cup Q_t$  % Combine  $P_t$  with  $Q_t$  to form  $R_t$  of size  $2N$ 
 $\mathcal{F} = \text{non\_dominated\_sorting}(R_t)$  % Identify non-dominated fronts  $\mathcal{F}_i$ ,  $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, etc.$ 
crowding\_distance\_assignment( $\mathcal{F}$ ) % Calculate crowding distance for each front  $\mathcal{F}_i$ 
 $P_t = \text{reduction}(R_t, \mathcal{F})$  % New population of parents of size  $N$ , from the reduction of  $R_t$ 
WHILE  $t \leq \text{gen}$  % If the maximum number of generations is reached
     $Q_t = \text{genetic\_operators}(P_t, \mathcal{F})$  % Create an offspring population by applying genetic operators to  $P_t$ 
     $R_t = P_t \cup Q_t$  % Combine  $P_t$  with  $Q_t$  to form  $R_t$  of size  $2N$ 
     $\mathcal{F} = \text{non\_dominated\_sorting}(R_t)$  % Identify non-dominated fronts  $\mathcal{F}_i$ ,  $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, etc.$ 
    crowding\_distance\_assignment( $\mathcal{F}$ ) % Calculate crowding distance for each front  $\mathcal{F}_i$ 
     $P_t = \text{reduction}(R_t, \mathcal{F})$  % New population of parents of size  $N$ , from the reduction of  $R_t$ 
     $t = t + 1$  % Increase generation counter
END
```

% Pareto optimal solutions are the non-dominated solutions of R_t , when $t = \text{gen}$

% MOPSO Algorithm

```
FOR  $i = 1$  to MAX
    Initialize POP( $i$ )
     $VEL(i) = 0$ 
    Evaluate POP( $i$ )
     $P_{best}(i) = POP(i)$ 
END
Initialize REP
ITE = 1
WHILE  $ITE \leq \text{MAXITE}$ 
    FOR  $i = 1$  to MAX
         $VEL(i) = \omega * VEL(i) + [c_1 * r_1 * (P_{best}(i) - POP(i))] + [c_2 * r_2 * (REP(h) - POP(i))]$ 
         $POP(i) = POP(i) + VEL(i)$ 
         $LB(i) \leq POP(i) \leq UB(i)$ 
        Mutate POP( $i$ )
        Evaluate POP( $i$ )
        IF  $POP(i) < P_{best}(i)$ 
             $P_{best}(i) = POP(i)$ 
        END
    END
    Update REP
     $ITE = ITE + 1$ 
END
```

% Pareto optimal solutions are the solutions stored in *Rep*, when $ITE = \text{MAXITE}$

% AMOSA Algorithm

Define: T_{max} , T_{min} , HL , SL , $iter$, α , $temp = T_{max}$

Initialize Archive

$current_pt = random(Archive)$ % Randomly chosen solution from the archive

WHILE ($temp > T_{min}$)

FOR $i = 1$ to $iter$

$new_pt = perturb(current_pt)$

 % Check the domination status of new_pt and $current_pt$

IF ($current_pt$ dominates new_pt) % Case 1

$\Delta dom_{avg} = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^k \Delta dom_{i,new_pt}) + \Delta dom_{current_pt,new_pt}}{k+1}$ % k : number of points in the archive which dominate new_pt , $k \geq 0$

$prob = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\Delta dom_{avg} * temp)}$

 Set new_pt as $current_pt$ with probability = $prob$

ELSEIF ($current_pt$ and new_pt are non-dominating to each other) % Case 2

 % Check the domination status of new_pt and points in the archive

IF (new_pt is dominated by k points in the archive, $k \geq 1$) % Case 2(a)

$\Delta dom_{avg} = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^k \Delta dom_{i,new_pt})}{k}$

$prob = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(\Delta dom_{avg} * temp)}$

 Set new_pt as $current_pt$ with probability = $prob$

ELSEIF (new_pt is non-dominating concerning all points in the archive) % Case 2(b)

 Set new_pt as $current_pt$ and add new_pt to the archive

IF ($Archive\ size > SL$)

 Cluster Archive to HL number of clusters

END

ELSEIF (new_pt dominates k points in the archive, $k \geq 1$) % Case 2(c)

 Set new_pt as $current_pt$ and add new_pt to the archive

 Remove all the k dominated points from the archive

END

ELSEIF (new_pt dominates $current_pt$) % Case 3

 % Check the domination status of new_pt and points in the archive

IF (new_pt is dominated by k points in the archive, $k \geq 1$) % Case 3(a)

Δdom_{min} = minimum of the difference of domination amounts between the new_pt and the k points

$prob = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\Delta dom_{min})}$

 Set point of the archive which corresponds to Δdom_{min} as $current_pt$ con with probability = $prob$, else set new_pt as $current_pt$

ELSEIF (new_pt is non-dominating for all points in the archive) % Case 3(b)

 Set new_pt as the $current_pt$ and add new_pt to the archive

 If $current_pt$ is in the archive, remove it from the archive

IF ($Archive\ size > SL$)

 Cluster Archive to HL number of clusters

END

ELSEIF (new_pt dominates k points in the archive, $k \geq 1$) % Case 3(c)

 Set new_pt as the $current_pt$ and add new_pt to the archive

 Remove all the k dominated points from the archive

END

END

$temp = \alpha * temp$

END

IF ($Archive\ size > SL$)

 Cluster Archive to HL number of clusters

END

% Pareto optimal solutions are the solutions stored in the Archive $temp < T_{min}$